

User Manual – CorrMic1 Grain Acquisition

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0. Try to avoid touching the mount surface with your fingers and clean with ethanol and compressed air if required. First, use compressed air to remove dust from the surface. Afterward, use a Kimtech wipe and a few drops of ethanol and wipe very softly over the grain surface (only ones). Use tweezers or gloves to handle the mount and clean surfaces around the microscope before analysing.

1. Use Tesa Tack to fix the sample on a glass slide.

2. Power the microscope by switching on both switches of the PSU, turn on the Laser (with the key) and the power plug on the anti-vibration table. Start the PC ones the laser light on the PSU is off and open the ZEN 3.5 (blue edition) software. Choose the following options while ZEN is initializing: 'ZEN system', 'Acquire New Image' and 'Calibrate Now'.

3. Place the sample under the microscope (after setting the stage in load position, lower black button on the right of the microscope). Return the stage to the normal position using the black 'up' arrow on the side of the microscope have a quick look at the sample, use 'Make it visible' option on the microscope tab.

4. Visually control if there are enough suitable grains for the analysis. If yes continue...

5. In the ZEN software start 'Macro/CorrMic1 Grain Acquisition'

6. Give the name of the Mount and select the location to store the data, e.g. Sample001 and store in D:/FissionTrack/MyProject/

7. Select the experimental method to use for the overview experiment (FT_OV_RL_BF_10x), the reflected light images (FT_RL_BF_100x) and transmissive light images (FT_TL_BF_100x).

8. You will be asked to open the 'Advanced Tile Viewer' which can be found in the 'Tiles' tab on the left of the screen.

9. The overview image will be compiled, go to the upper left and lower right corners of the mount. Make sure you are in focus in the center of the mount.

10. In case the images are too light/dark, use the 'Exposure' tab or adjust the lighting at the microscope. These changes need to be saved in the experiment (can be found on the top left of the screen).

11. Next step is to select three glass beads that roughly form an isosceles triangle and are not too close to the border of the mount (2-3 mm distance). Note that you might need to stop and re-start live view to get into live view.

12. After doing the fine positioning of the reference points, make a screenshot of the tile image and positions of reference points at low magnification.

13. To navigate on the overview image, open Tiles/Show viewer and drag/drop the mount image on the Tile Viewer.

14. Start 'Live' and navigate on the mount by double-clicking on the grain you want to have a look at. The microscope will change from 5x to 100x objective and you should decide if you want to continue or discard the grain. In both cases the location of discarded (yellow circle) and selected grains (green circle) is marked on the mount image.

15. You have to focus on the grain surface and afterwards about 20 microns into the grain (at least as deep as the fission tracks). A transmitted z-stack, a reflected EFI is taken by merging images around the surface and an overview image is taken with 5x. The last one is saved in the main folder and should be used to correctly place the laser spot in Geostar (RESOLUTION laser).

16. Repeat the procedure until you have e.g. 20 grains (bedrock sample) or 100 grains (detrital sample).

17. When you are finished, set the objective lens back to 5x, cover the microscope, and switch off the power supplies first to the computer, then turn off the laser, and then turn off the power supplied to the laser.

- 1) Up down switch to move the stage (after sending to load position)
- 2) Brightness light dial
- 3) Focus wheel
- 4) Slide switch that changes amount of light that is transmitted to sample
- 5) Power supply to laser
- 6) Laser
- 7) Power strip to computer and microscope
- 8) Display screen (make it visible)
- 9) Computer and power button
- 10) Place to load sample--stage